

Decentralized Placement of Heterogeneous Nodes

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I. ABSTRACT

We present a node placement algorithm for planning the deployment of a heterogeneous, underwater sensor network. Typical node placement algorithms do not account for heterogeneous node types and consequently, do not always provide accurate estimates for the total probability of success for the overall mission objective. In our approach, we derive an objective function that couples the probability of success for all node types to be used by a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) solver for optimal placement. To reduce the computational intensity associated with the MILP-based approach, we provide an algorithm that converts the original optimization problem into several smaller optimization problems. We also describe the accompanying MILP framework that we have developed to create and maintain MILP problems.

II. INTRODUCTION

As node types are created, node placement algorithms must adjust to account for the new node types if an optimal placement solution is desired. We have developed a MILP-based algorithm that optimally places multiple sensors and a single effector as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Example mission. For phase 1, the effector enters the field. In phase 2, the effector autonomously places the sensors. In phase 3, the effector bottoms itself to await phase 4, in which the effector will affect the detected maritime asset.

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To accommodate the placement of heterogeneous nodes, we have developed an objective function that considers the probabilistic performance of both the effector and sensor. The objective function is nonlinear and is approximated by piecewise linear functions, which increases the number of binary constraints. Our decentralized algorithm reduces the number of binary constraints associated with a single problem by solving several smaller problems in which small subsets of nodes are optimally placed. Furthermore, to assist with the creation and maintenance of the constraints, we have developed a MILP framework that uses a publish-subscribe pattern and state machine to manage the phases of constraint development.

Optimization of sensor locations has been studied in several fields. A variety of approaches exist including various geometric schemes for static underwater sensor deployment [1], [2], as well as a clustering approach to maintain coverage through redundant clustered sensors [3], [4]. In [5], Mukherjee et al. solved the sensor placement problem as a multiobjective optimization problem using elements from statistical mechanics to achieve a low-dimensional representation of the sensor distribution. Jourdan and Weck developed a genetic algorithm to optimize total sensor coverage and lifetime of the network for wireless sensor networks [6]. Kukunuru, Thella, and Davuluri used a particle swarm approach to optimize sensor locations of a wireless sensor network to provide good coverage [7]. Akkaya and Younis employed clustering techniques to minimize the latency of data transference, while maximizing the coverage area of the entire wireless network [8]. More recently, Ibrahim et al. employed a MILP approach to minimize overall delay of packet transmission, energy consumption, and average delay of packet [9]. In the field of water contamination, Watson et al. developed MILP formulations to optimize sensor locations to detect malicious contaminants that were introduced into the water supply [10], [11]. In [12]–[14], the authors used gradient-based methods to optimize sensor coverage of mobile agents. Wolf, Moura, and Krstic developed a system of Partial Differential Equations (PDEs) and used a nonlinear solver to optimize the location of sensors used to monitor battery temperature dynamics [15].

While the current methods used to determine sensor placement perform well with respect to their particular applications, they also have limitations. Although particle swarm approaches can converge faster than genetic algorithms, both genetic algorithms [16] and particle swarm approaches [17] can have problems with convergence to suboptimal solutions. Gradient methods can suffer from slow convergence, although this can be avoided by using preconditioning. The

preconditioning steps can be prohibitively expensive [18] and are avoidable with MILP-based methods.

The remainder of our paper is organized as follows. Section III describes our objective function. Section IV describes our decentralized algorithm for heterogeneous node placement, while Sections V and VI describe key details related to integration constraints and the framework for which the problem was encoded. Section VII shows the results of our simulations and Section VIII contains our conclusions.

III. PROBABILITY OF SUCCESS

For the purpose of discussion, we suppose that we have two different types of nodes and now describe an objective function that measures the total probability of a successfully detecting and affecting ship arrival traffic. The two types of nodes for this mission are the sensor node and the effector. The total probability of success naturally depends upon the performance of all deployed nodes, as well as the ship traffic arrival distribution. For an operation area $B \subset \mathbb{R}^3$, let us assume that sensors and effector are defined by the following.

Definition 3.1: (Sensor) For sensor position

$$p_{s_i} = (x_{s_i}, y_{s_i}, d) \in B, \quad (1)$$

environmental vector $e \in E_{env} \subset \mathbb{R}^m$, and $\tau \in B$, the probability of detection at τ is given as $\rho(p_{s_i}, e, \tau)$ where $\rho : B \times E_{env} \times B \rightarrow [0, 1]$. For $\rho \geq \rho_{min}$, the i -th sensing region is defined as

$$\mathcal{S}_i = \{\tau \in B : \rho(p_{s_i}, e, \tau) \geq \rho_{min}\} \cap \mathcal{P}, \quad (2)$$

where \mathcal{P} is the plane for which the arrival traffic operates.

Definition 3.2: (effector) For effector w , sensor position p_{s_i} , effector position

$$p_w = (x_w, y_w, d) \in B, \quad (3)$$

environmental vector $e \in \mathbb{R}^m$, and $\tau \in B$, $\nu(p_{s_i}, p_w, e, \tau)$ is the probability of successfully completing an action at τ where $\nu : B \times B \times E_{env} \times B \rightarrow [0, 1]$. For $\nu \geq \nu_{min}$, the i -th effector region is defined as

$$\mathcal{W}_i = \{\tau \in B : \nu(p_{s_i}, p_w, e, \tau) \geq \nu_{min}\} \cap \mathcal{P} \subset B. \quad (4)$$

In other words, we are defining the performance of both sensor and effector relative to the sensor. This simple, yet effective technique allows us to easily define the composite performance of each sensor and the effector by using the intersection of these regions. If we assume that the traffic distribution is given as \mathcal{A} , and that traffic does not change direction inside of B , then a good measure of success would be to compute the probability of traffic arrival, detection, and effector impact. Therefore, we want to know the joint probability distribution function $p(\chi_A, \chi_D, \chi_E)$, where χ_A, χ_D, χ_E are random variables describing the arrival distribution of traffic, detection, and effecting events, respectively. For M sensors, our objective function takes the more continuous form

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \int_{I_i} \mathcal{A}(x) \cdot p(\chi_D, \chi_E | \chi_A) dx, \quad (5)$$

where $\mathcal{A}(x) = p(\chi_A)$, $I_i = \mathcal{P}_B(\mathcal{S}_i \cap \mathcal{W}_i)$ and \mathcal{P}_B is the orthogonal projector onto the boundary line of B for which the traffic enters.

We consider the case for which the χ_A, χ_D , and χ_E are independent, and the computation is straightforward, except for one complication. Sensors that provide overlapping coverage increase the probability of success and therefore must be addressed. For intervals that are created from the overlap of κ intervals, we define the following sets:

$$L_\kappa = \{l : l = \cap_{k=1}^\kappa I_{\alpha_k} - \cup_{j \neq \alpha_k} (\cap_{k=1}^\kappa I_{\alpha_k}) \cap I_j\} \quad (6)$$

We can compute the probability of successfully detecting and assisting a distressed vehicle with i overlapping intervals as

$$p_i = 1 - (1 - p)^i, \quad (7)$$

where $p = \rho_{min} \cdot \kappa_{min}$, giving rise to the following objective function

$$P_s = \sum_{k=1}^M p_k \int_{l \in L_k} \mathcal{A}(x) dx. \quad (8)$$

Using numerical techniques, we can construct a linear approximation to the integral such that

$$P_s \approx \sum_{k=1}^M p_k \sum_{l \in L_k} (F(\alpha_k) - F(\beta_k)), \quad (9)$$

where $l = [\alpha_k, \beta_k]$ and F is a piecewise linear approximation to the integral of $\mathcal{A}(x)$. Therefore, assuming the existence of F , our optimization problem can be stated as

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{(x_{s_i}, y_{s_i})}{\text{maximize}} && \sum_{k=1}^M p_k \sum_{l \in L_k} (F(\alpha_k) - F(\beta_k)) \\ & \text{subject to} && g(x_{s_i}, y_{s_i}) \leq b_j, j = 1 \cdots m, \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where $g(x_{s_i}, y_{s_i})$ are linear functions.

IV. DECENTRALIZED ALGORITHM

The objective function is computationally difficult to manage, as additional sensors multiply the number of constraints associated with the number of intervals of the arrival distribution. To address this problem, we employ a heuristic to reduce the complexity. Rather than attempting to optimize the location of all of the sensors and the effector, we will use multiple iterations in which we optimize the locations of groups of sensors. We can rewrite the objective function given by (8) as

$$P_s = p \sum_i^N \sum_j^{M_i} \int_{I_j^{(i)}} \mathcal{A}^{(i)}(x) dx, \quad (11)$$

where $I_j^{(i)}$ is the interval corresponding to the j -th sensor of the i -th group or iteration, N is the number of iterations, M_i is the number sensors for the i -th iteration, and $\mathcal{A}^{(i)}$ is given as

$$A^{(i)}(x) = \begin{cases} (1 - p)^{i-1} \mathcal{A}(x)^{(i-1)} & , x \in I_j^{(i)} \\ A^{(i-1)}(x) & , x \notin I_j^{(i)} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

where $\cap_j I_j^{(i)} \neq \emptyset$ for all i . If we have k intersections, then there exists $I_{j_i}^{(i)}$ such that $x \in I_{j_i}^{(i)}$, which implies that $\mathcal{A}^{(i)}(x) = (1-p)^{k-1} \mathcal{A}(x)$. Since we have k intersections, then we also have $1, \dots, k-1$ intersections and the total probability of success attributed to all of these events at x is given by $(1 - (1-p)^k) \mathcal{A}(x)$. If we integrate over all of the intervals for which we have k intersections, then we see that we get the probability of success given by

$$\int_{l \in L_k} \mathcal{A}(x) dx,$$

and if we sum over all k , then we get (8). Thus, we can write the final form of our objective function as

$$\begin{aligned} & \underset{(x_{s_i}, y_{s_i})}{\text{maximize}} && \sum_i^N \sum_j^{M_i} (F^{(i)}(\alpha_{ij}) - F^{(i)}(\beta_{ij})) \\ & \text{subject to} && g(x_{s_i}, y_{s_i}) \leq b_j, j = 1 \dots m, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where $F^{(i)}$ is a piecewise linear approximation to the integral of $\mathcal{A}^{(i)}(x)$, $\alpha_{ij} = x_{s_{ij}} + r_{ij}$, and $\beta_{ij} = x_{s_{ij}} - r_{ij}$. Please note that s_{ij} refers to the j -th sensor placed during the i -th iteration, and $x_{s_{ij}}$ and r_{ij} are the position and radius of sensor s_{ij} , respectively. As a matter of implementation, (12) implies that we need to adjust \mathcal{A} by a factor of $1-p$ before the next group is placed. Notice that we do not allow for overlap within a group of sensors being placed for each iteration, which permits a reduction in computational complexity. However, overlap between iterations is allowed.

V. INTEGRAL CONSTRAINTS

As the numerical integration constraints comprise the main constraints for which we need to represent, we now discuss our approach to their MILP representation. To represent an estimate of the integral provided by the objective function, we will combine some techniques of MILP programming with those of numerical integration techniques. We first show how to represent the definite integral of $\mathcal{A}(x)$ evaluated at the upper bound given by α_{ij} , and apply the same techniques to compute the lower bound. We begin with a partition of the traffic boundary

$$T = \{x_0, x_1, \dots, x_{\nu-1}, x_{\nu}\},$$

where ν is the number of required rectangles. The left Riemann sum is given by

$$F^{(i)}(\alpha_{ij}) = \mathcal{A}^{(i)}(x)(\alpha_{ij} - x_h) + \sum_{k=0}^{h-1} \mathcal{A}^{(i)}(x_k), \quad (14)$$

where $x_h \leq \alpha_{ij} \leq x_{h+1}$. For each interval $[x_h, x_{h+1}]$, we introduce the continuous variable ξ_{ijh} that can assume any value in $[x_h, x_{h+1}]$. To ensure that $\xi_{ijh} \in [x_h, x_{h+1}]$, we use the binary variable

$$b_{ijh} = \begin{cases} 1 & , x \in [x_h, x_{h+1}] \\ 0 & , x \notin [x_h, x_{h+1}] \end{cases}.$$

Since we require $b_{ijh} \implies x_{s_{ij}} + r_{ij} \in [x_h, x_{h+1}]$, we have

$$\forall 1 \leq i \leq N, 0 \leq j \leq M_i,$$

$$\sum_{h=0}^{\nu-1} \xi_{ijh} = x_{s_{ij}} + r_{ij}, \quad (15)$$

$$\sum_{h=0}^{\nu-1} b_{ijh} = 1, \quad (16)$$

$$x_h b_{ijh} \leq \xi_{ijh}, \quad (17)$$

$$\xi_{ijh} \leq x_{h+1} b_{ijh}. \quad (18)$$

We can now rewrite (14) as

$$F^{(i)}(x_{s_{ij}} + r_{ij}) = \sum_{h=0}^{\nu-1} (b_{ijh} \xi_{ijh} + \mathcal{A}^{(i)}(x_h) \xi_{ijh}), \quad (19)$$

where

$$\xi_{ijh} = -x_h \mathcal{A}^{(i)}(x_h) + \sum_{k=0}^{h-1} \mathcal{A}^{(i)}(x_k)(x_{k+1} - x_k). \quad (20)$$

For the lower bound $F^{(i)}(\beta_{ij})$, we introduce analogous variables b'_{ijj} , ζ'_{ijh} , and ξ'_{ijh} and have

$$F^{(i)}(x_{s_{ij}} - r_{ij}) = \sum_{h=0}^{\nu-1} (b'_{ijh} + \mathcal{A}^{(i)}(x_h) \xi'_{ijh}), \quad (21)$$

and

$$\zeta'_{ijh} = -x_h \mathcal{A}^{(i)}(x_h) + \sum_{k=0}^{h-1} \mathcal{A}^{(i)}(x_k)(x_{k+1} - x_k), \quad (22)$$

which are subject to similar constraints:

$$\forall 1 \leq i \leq N, 0 \leq j \leq M_i,$$

$$\sum_{h=0}^{\nu-1} \xi'_{ijh} = x_{s_{ij}} - r_{ij}, \quad (23)$$

$$\sum_{h=0}^{\nu-1} b'_{ijh} = 1, \quad (24)$$

$$x_h b'_{ijh} \leq \xi'_{ijh}, \quad (25)$$

$$\xi'_{ijh} \leq x_{h+1} b'_{ijh}. \quad (26)$$

VI. IMPLEMENTATION

Once the constraints are theoretically derived, they must be implemented and given to a MILP solver for computation to determine the optimal positions. However, constructing the constraints can be a tedious task, especially for solvers that are array-based, which require the user to maintain the mapping of variables into a variable array. To handle this, we have created a MILP framework that resides between our implementation and the solver as shown in Figure 2. This state machine layer is a middle layer between the developer and MILP solver and allows for three states that allow for the creation of variables, constraints, and the objective function. During the variable creation state, the state machine registers as a listener for each variable and as such, can receive notifications of changes of its value or associated coefficient.

Fig. 2: Framework for creating variables and constraints.

In the constraint creation state, constraints are individually created one at a time; as all of the variables are registered with the state machine, the developer can refer to each variable by a specific name, rather than via an index mapping that would have to be maintained otherwise. As an example, for the x coordinate of a particular sensor, originally, the developer would create the variable through the MILP solver and then maintain the index of the variable that is assigned by the solver. With the new architecture, the user can now just instantiate a variable called *sensorX* and refer to it directly by name when creating constraints. Using the variables defined in the variable creation state, the state machine allows the user to easily define the objective function during the create objective function state. The state machine enforces that users create all variables first, constraints second, and the objective function last. Attempting to violate this order results in exceptions that user must address.

VII. RESULTS

Using a field of size 2×1 distance units, and a sensor and effector threshold of .8 and .9 respectively, the algorithm was tested using a uniform arrival distribution, as well as a normal and a bimodal arrival distribution with randomly sampled parameters. Figure 3 is an example of placing 6 sensors within a field that assumes traffic is traversing the field from north to south with entry points sampled from a bimodal distribution.

To compare the results of the optimization routine, a Monte Carlo simulation was used to verify if the sensors and effector would indeed detect the and interact with the incoming traffic. Using a group size of 1 and varying the sensors from 1 to 50 with increments of 5 sensors, Figures 4 - 6 show that the algorithm compares well with the simulation. Note that we have 400 runs for each number of nodes. Observe that for all three distributions, we see that the objective value results are actually less than the Monte Carlo simulation, which is to be expected as our objective function provides a conservative estimate of the nonlinear objective function given by (8). Comparison of Figure 4 to Figures 5 and 6 show that the normal distribution requires less nodes to reach higher probabilities of success than the other two, which is to be expected as most of the normal distribution covers less of the incoming traffic boundary than the uniform and bimodal distributions.

Fig. 3: Example showing the placement of 6 sensors and effector within a 2×1 field that assumes traffic flows from north to south using bimodal entry points.

Fig. 4: Average of optimization runs using a normal arrival distribution and placing one sensor at a time.

In Figure 7, we have time comparisons that are averages over all of the runs for each number of nodes. For each distribution, we see a monotonic increase in computational time that seems higher than linear growth, due to other constraints that do not scale linearly with the number of nodes. As an example, the growth rate associated with constraints that describe standoff constraints between all sensors is unfortunately high as it depends upon the number of nodes that are placed, as well as the number of nodes to be placed. Another observation about this data is that the bimodal distribution requires more processing time than the normal distribution, which requires more processing time than the uniform distribution. The bimodal distribution requires more intervals than the normal distribution, and the normal distribution requires more intervals than the uniform distribution. Consequently, we expect to see analogous increases in computational times as there will be relative

Fig. 5: Average of optimization runs using a bimodal arrival distribution and placing one sensor at a time.

Fig. 6: Optimization runs using a uniform arrival distribution and placing one sensor at a time.

Fig. 7: Computational Time(seconds) for a group size of 1.

increases in the number of integer constraints required for

MILP representation.

Figures 8 - 10 show the results of optimizing two sensors per iteration. For these cases, we only have 30 runs per number of nodes. Unlike the single sensor cases, the optimization algorithm ran until the probability of success was close to 1, which is why some of the figures have different numbers of nodes. If we compare the results of optimizing 1 at a time versus two at a time, we see that the accuracy increases for the 2 nodes, but the time for computation increases significantly as shown in Figure 11. This is expected, as an increase in the group size substantially increases the number of constraints needed to represent additional sensors, thereby increasing the computational complexity.

Fig. 8: Average of optimization runs using a normal arrival distribution and placing two sensors at a time.

Fig. 9: Average of optimization runs using a bimodal arrival distribution and placing two sensors at a time.

VIII. CONCLUSIONS

We have introduced a decentralized method to optimize the placement of heterogeneous nodes and described its implementation within our MILP framework. The results presented show how that the algorithm can place at least

Fig. 10: Optimization runs using a uniform arrival distribution and placing two sensors at a time.

Fig. 11: Computational Time(seconds) for a group size of 2.

50 nodes for multiple types of arrival distributions. Through the validation of Monte Carlo simulations, we see that the results are very accurate. We also introduced our MILP framework and discussed how it can minimize the tedium associated with maintaining the variables and constraints associated with a MILP problem. For future work, we expect to produce proofs that validate the objective function used for optimization, as well as rigorously verify that our estimates provide a lower bound for the nonlinear objective function.

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